

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Here is another “regular” issue: “regular” in contrast to the many “special issues” that we have published over the last 3 years. Due to queries from readers and authors, we will publish a higher percentage of regular issues again in the future, however, this depends on whether YOU and your colleagues submit enough good papers!

The current issue seems to reflect that there is a new big area of research that I tend to call now “Web Science”. All papers except maybe papers 1 and 4 deal in some way with aspects of the Web and knowledge management!

The last three papers are actually extended and improved versions of the most excellent papers of the Triple-I conference that took place in Graz, and were especially selected and reviewed by Klaus Tochtermann and Gisela Granitzer from the KNOW- Center, www.know-center.at. The first of those three papers deals with knowledge portal development, highlighting the importance of the user. The authors claim the development to be driven by a subject-centric model. The last two articles pick up more traditional knowledge management themes: the second paper highlights the importance of integrating knowledge management into the development process of digital games. The third paper analyses which factors were responsible for the repeated failure of the Swedish Armed in their knowledge management efforts.

I want to thank all authors and reviewers for their cooperation, and wish all readers enjoyment and insight as they work thorough the papers.

And don't forget: we count on you to submit good material to our journal.

PS: Did you know that J.UCS has an estimated readership of over 80.000?

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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